

Synthesis and Biological Activity of Heterocyclic Derivatives derived from Ethyl-2-hydroxy-quinoxaline-3-carboxylate

P. S. FERNANDES* and T. M. SONAR

Nadkarny-Sacasa Research Laboratories, St. Xavier's College, Mahapalika Marg, Bombay-400 001

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Ethyl-2-chloroquinoxaline-3-carboxylate obtained from ethyl-2-hydroxyquinoxaline-3-carboxylate upon treatment with morpholine gave ethyl-2-morpholinoquinoxaline-3-carboxylate (1). This ester upon reaction with hydrazine hydrate (99%) gave respective carboxy hydrazide (2). This hydrazide on reaction with phenyl isothiocyanates gave thiosemicarbazides (3a-c). The thiosemicarbazides on reaction with concentrated sulphuric acid or anhydrous phosphoric acid gave 2-(4-substituted)-anilino-5-((2'-morpholino)quinoxalino)-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (4a-c). The thiosemicarbazides on reaction with 4% sodium hydroxide formed 4-(*para*-substituted-phenyl)-3-mercapto-5-((2'-morpholino)quinoxalino)-1,2,4-triazoles (5a-c), and on reaction with I_2 in KI gave 2-(4-substituted)anilino-5-((2'-morpholino)quinoxalino)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (6a-c) respectively.

SEVERAL biologically active polypeptides, such as levomycin, actinoleukin and echinomycin have been shown to possess one or more quinoxalinoyl residues¹. Echinomycin possesses antitumour, antiviral, and antibacterial activities but its low therapeutic index has precluded any medicinal uses.

Thiosemicarbazides in general are known for their antitubercular², antifungal^{2,3} and hypoglycemic⁴ properties. In view of these, we felt, it is worth synthesising thiosemicarbazides of substituted quinoxaline series. Thiosemicarbazides are further reacted to give corresponding oxadiazoles, thiadiazoles, and triazoles. All compounds synthesised were screened for their antibacterial properties.

Ethyl-2-chloro-quinoxaline-3-carboxylate was prepared according to the reported procedures⁵. This compound upon reaction with morpholine in methanol gave ethyl-2-morpholino-quinoxaline-3-carboxylate (1) in good yields. Its structure was confirmed by ir, nmr and mass spectra. 1 showed a sharp peak at 1720 cm^{-1} in its ir spectrum indicating the presence of an ester carbonyl group. Support for the structure was obtained from 1H nmr spectra ($CDCl_3$) of 1 where CH_2 protons are found as triplet at δ 1.4, CH_3 as a quartet at 4.45, CH_2 adjacent to N (morpholino) as triplet at 3.55, CH_2 adjacent to O as a triplet at 3.8 and aromatic protons as a multiplet at 7.75.

Ethyl-2-morpholinoquinoxaline-3-carboxylate upon reaction with hydrazine hydrate (99%) gave the corresponding carboxy hydrazide (2) in fairly good yields. Its structure was confirmed by ir, nmr and mass spectra. 2 showed a sharp peak at 1650 ($C=O$) and 3320 cm^{-1} (NH) in its ir spectrum. The structure was confirmed from 1H nmr spectra ($CDCl_3$) of 2 where CH_2 protons (adjacent to N of

morpholino group) are found as a triplet at δ 3.5, CH_2 adjacent to O (morpholino group) are occurring as a triplet at 3.85, four aromatic protons as a multiplet at 7.7, NH_2 protons of hydrazide as a singlet at 4.05 and NH protons of hydrazide are seen as a singlet at 8.6.

Hydrazide 2 was allowed to react with substituted phenyl isothiocyanate to give corresponding thiosemicarbazides (3a-c). The broad peaks in the ir spectra of 3a at 3000-3220 cm^{-1} may be due to NH functions and the peaks at 1270 cm^{-1} are assigned to C=S functions.

The thiosemicarbazides on reaction with concentrated H_2SO_4 or a phosphoric acid undergoes a cyclodehydration to give 2-(4-substituted)-anilino-5-((2'-morpholino)quinoxalino)-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (4a-c). The ir spectrum of 4a showed peaks at 3200 cm^{-1} and 2980 cm^{-1} due to two NH groups. The peaks at 1540 and 1580 cm^{-1} clearly indicate the conjugated C=N with the absence of C=O.

The thiosemicarbazides upon refluxing with 4% sodium hydroxide gave 4-(*para*-substituted-phenyl)-3-mercapto-5-((2'-morpholino)quinoxalino)-1,2,4-triazoles (5a-c). The ir spectrum of 5a showed the absence of NH and C=O functions. Appearance of a peak due to conjugated C=N at 1595 and 1605 cm^{-1} , is in conformity with the structures (5a-c). Thiosemicarbazide upon reaction with I_2 in KI gave 2-(4-substituted)-anilino-5-((2'-morpholino)quinoxalino)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (6a-c). 6a exhibited all the characteristic features in ir like NH at 3200 cm^{-1} , absence of a peak due to C=O and peaks at 1560 and 1590 cm^{-1} due to conjugated C=N is observed. This suggests that the thiosemicarbazides have undergone oxidation to give the substituted oxadiazoles (6a-c).

Physical data are given in Table 1 and various reactions involved in Scheme 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-MORPHOLINOQUINOXALINE-3-THIOSEMICARBAZIDE (3a-c), 2-(4-SUBSTITUTED)-ANILINO-5-((2'-MORPHOLINO)QUINOXALINO)-1,3,4-THIADIAZOLE (4a-c), 4-(*para*-SUBSTITUTED-PHENYL)-3-MERCAPTO-5-((2'-MORPHOLINO)QUINOXALINO)-1,2,4-TRIAZOLES (5a-c), AND 2-(4-SUBSTITUTED)-ANILINO-5-((2'-MORPHOLINO)QUINOXALINO)-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLES (6a-c)

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %
3a	201	58
3b	182	76
3c	162	93
4a	213	63
4b	240	77
4c	284	89
5a	235	21
5b	260	70
5c	95	35
6a	192d	72
6b	188	83
6c	156	81

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 633 spectrophotometer. For compounds 1 and 2 nmr and mass spectra were taken on Varian FT 80 and Varian 114 MAT instruments, respectively. All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

Ethyl-2-morpholinoquinoxaline-3-carboxylate (1) : Diethyl malonate was oxidised with nitrous oxide to give ethyl oxomalonate⁶, which upon condensation with *o*-phenylenediamine gave ethyl-2-hydroxyquinoxaline-3-carboxylate. This compound upon reaction with phosphorous oxychloride gave ethyl-2-chloroquinoxaline-3-carboxylate.

To a methanolic solution of the above crude chloro compound (0.01 mol), morpholine (0.01 mol) was added and refluxed for 2 h. Solvent was then removed under vacuum and the contents extracted with hot petroleum ether. Petroleum ether extracts were concentrated and cooled to 0° under vigorous stirring for 1 h to get the crude product, which was filtered and recrystallised from 70% methanol to get ethyl-2-morpholinoquinoxaline-3-carboxylate (34%), m.p. 66°.

2-Morpholino-quinoxaline-3-carboxy hydrazide (2) : The above prepared ethyl-2-morpholinoquinoxaline-3-carboxylate (0.01 mol), methanol (50 ml), and hydrazine hydrate (0.015 mol) were refluxed on a water-bath for 8 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated under vacuum. Resultant mass was cooled to 0° for 1 h. Ice-cold water (10 ml) was then added to the solution under stirring. The solid that separated out was filtered and crystallised from ethanol (activated charcoal used) to give the corresponding hydrazide (73%), m.p. 180°.

2-Morpholinoquinoxaline-3-thiosemicarbazide (3a-c) : Carboxy hydrazide (2; 0.001 mol) in ethanol

Scheme 1

(100 ml) was dissolved by heating. To it appropriate phenyl isothiocyanate⁷ (0.001 mol) was added with stirring and then refluxed on water-bath for 3 h. Reaction mixture was concentrated to 1/3 volume and cooled. The solid separated out was collected by filtration and crystallised from ethanol to get 3a-c.

2-(4-Substituted)anilino-5-((2'-morpholino)quinoxalino)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (4a-c) :

For compounds 4a and 4c : The appropriate thiosemicarbazide (3a, 3c) (0.001 mol) was added in small portions to concentrated sulphuric acid (25 ml) at 0°. The mixture was kept stirring for

1 h. It was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature, and then poured carefully into crushed ice. To it under cooling, 10% liquor ammonia was added till pH was neutral. The solid separated was filtered, washed with ice-cold water and crystallised from ethanol.

For compound 4b: Thiosemicarbazide (3b; 0.001 mol) was added with stirring to anhydrous phosphoric acid (20 ml) during 20 min. It was heated on an oil-bath at 120° for 0.5 h, then cooled to room temperature and reaction mass poured over crushed ice. To it under stirring, 10% ammonia was added till pH became neutral. The solid separated was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol.

4-(para-Substituted-phenyl)-3 mercapto-5-((2'-morpholino)quinoxalino)-1,2,4-triazoles (5a-c): The appropriate thiosemicarbazide (3a-c; 0.001 mol) and 2N sodium hydroxide (20 ml) were refluxed for 3 h. The solution was cooled, filtered and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The desired compound thus precipitated was filtered, washed with water and crystallised.

2-(4-Substituted)-anilino-5((2'-morpholino)quinoxalino)-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (6a-c): Thiosemicarbazides (3a-c; 0.001 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) were added to NaOH (5 ml, 4N), with cooling and shaking. A solution of iodine in KI was added dropwise with stirring and cooling till the colour of iodine persisted. The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 4 h and more iodine solution was added to maintain a permanent tinge of iodine. The solvent was distilled off. The reaction mixture was cooled, poured into ice-water. pH of the solu-

tion was made acidic by adding dilute HCl. The solid separated was filtered, washed with dilute solution of sodium thiosulphate and then with little cold water and crystallised.

Biological activity: The compounds (Table 1) were evaluated for their antibacterial activity by ditch plate technique⁸, using concentration levels 2, 3 and 5 mg ml⁻¹. The test organisms employed were *Salmonella typhi*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli* and *Bacillus subtilis*. Activity levels at concentration of 2 and 3 mg ml⁻¹ were negligible in most cases. Compounds 5c and 6c were found to inhibit all the organisms tested, though the activity against *P. aeruginosa* and *B. subtilis* were negligible. 3c was active in all the organism at a concentration of 5 mg ml⁻¹. 5a and 2 were totally inactive against all the organisms. 4c though inactive against the rest showed very promising activity against *Salmonella* species

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